

The importance of business environment in logistics transport development: Ho Chi Minh, Vietnam

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Abstract: There is a variety of factors impact on business environment, they are in different way to impact on. Objective of the paper is to analyse the importance of business environment in logistics transport development by assess three variables are investment of government, foreign investment and economy openness in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam (HCM). Author uses Multivariate regression (MR) with time series data between 2010 and 2020. The main findings are while investment from the government budget and foreign investment impact, openness of economy does not impact on Labour goods productivity. While investment from the government budget and foreign investment impact, openness of economy does not impact on Labour passenger productivity. While foreign investment impacts, investment from the government budget and openness of economy do not impact on Capital goods productivity. While foreign investment impacts, investment from the government budget and openness of economy do not impact on Capital passenger productivity. While investment from the government budget and foreign investment impact, openness of economy does not impact on Gross domestic products.

Key words: business environment, logistics, transport, development, HCM, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

I. Introduction

Investment to business environment is considered the official driver of economic growth and the nature of this relationship has been studied in many theoretical and experimental studies. There are many studies distinguish between private investment and public investment, whereby public investment is often thought of as investment in infrastructure. Such a distinction is significant because investment in infrastructure is different from the capital used in enterprises, firms, business activities. Infrastructure is capital that exists outside of a business and supports the economic activities of businesses. As a result, many businesses are in an area get benefits from that infrastructure at no additional cost or at least at a lower cost if the infrastructure has to be made available to users. In addition, the infrastructure can be seen as providing extraneous benefits to those users. This paper analysis the role of investment of government in business environment like logistics transport infrastructure, general administrative and public services in logistics transport sector in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam (HCM).

Helde A.D. Hdom, Jose Alberto Fuinhas (2020) found that "Electricity generation, GDP and trade liberalization have both positive and negative effects on Brazil's economy. We also discovered a bi-directional causality between trade openness and all the energies produced in Brazil. Separately, we observed that GDP, hydropower, and renewables have negative effects on the CO2 emissions model, while only emissions of pollution and trade openness have positive effects on the economic growth model". There is a long-run effects of energy-mix, trade openness, research and development on the economic output of G20 countries. Trade openness, research and development are found to be the contributing factors in enhancing economic output for almost countries. The increasing roles of renewable sources are prominent in Argentina, Germany, Indonesia, Italy, the Russian Federation, and the United States; while in Australia, Brazil, Canada, France, Japan, South Korea and Mexico, there is a negative relationship with output (Arjita Sikder, John Inekwe, Mita Bhattacharya, 2019). Kazi Sohag, Rawshan Ara Begum, Sharifah Mastura Syed Abdullah et al., (2015) found that "Increasing GDP per capita and trade openness produce a rebound effect of technological innovation on energy use". Through analysis, the efficiency of total logistics transport investment in a sample of 34 countries over the period 1996 to 2010. By evaluating countries according to their ability to achieve the maximum attainable infrastructure quantity and usage for a given investment volume. It is found that the Central European countries, New Zealand and Japan are the

most efficient when investing in transport infrastructure while the Eastern European countries, Russia, Turkey and Mexico are the least. Conclusion is the role of quality of government is positive impact to investment in business environment and the efficiency of logistics transport infrastructure (Andreas P. Kyriacou, Leonel Muinelo-Gallo, Oriol Roca-Sagalés, 2019).

The content of paper has eight sections; section 1, section 2, section 3, section 4, section 5, section 6, section 7 and section 8 are introduction, literature review, methodology, theoretical basis, data source, study results, discussion and conclusion, respectively.

II. Literature review

Variables of business environment at the sub-national level in explaining firm employment and productivity growth consists of finance and infrastructure, and the existence of a strong agglomeration environment to be critically important (Jose-Daniel Reyes, Mark Roberts, Lixin Colin Xu, 2021). According to Christine ZhenweiQiang, He Wang, L. Colin Xu (2021) that "Four aspects of the business environment are found to be relatively robust by multiple data sources: access to finance, electricity, internet, and human capital. The effects of de jure business environment indicators on firm performances depend on measures of contract enforcement. Foreign-owned firms benefit more from the maintenance of physical safety and ease in obtaining construction permits, gain competitive advantage in productivity when domestic infrastructure or access to finance is worse". Low input costs, easy access to finance and a good level of sophistication and business innovation in a competitive and productive small and medium enterprises sector must be associated with complex and innovative business environments (Erick Ariel Gonzales Rocha, 2012). As in study by Monica Escaleras, Eric P. Chiang (2017) that "Fiscal decentralization improves the business environment and the effect is strongest among lower-income countries". In China, Government plays big role in strengthening environmental protection investment such as making system innovation on environmental investment, including administrative and financial environmental affairs, giving fair treatment of investor, business environment. Environmental fund for special purposes and environmental taxes (Zhang Wei, Wen Hongyu, Zhang Dandan, 2011). The R&D investment intensity has a significant positive correlation with the financial competitiveness to new energy listed companies in China (Zhihong Zhu, Zhiwei Zhu, Ping Xu et al., 2019). Japanese direct investment in the United States has dramatically increased in the 1980s, particularly since 1985. All the Japanese direct investment in the United States that is more than 60% occurred in the second half of the decade. Export promotional activities of state government are effective in attracting Japanese investments (Masaaki Kotabe, 1993). The role of government in promoting private investment that can be assessed through two dimensions which are size of government and governance quality. Public governance remains a big challenge in Vietnam's private sector development policies. Changes of public governance quality is crucial to improve the effects of government size on private investment (Thanh DinhSu, Thi Mai Hoai Bui, 2017).

Regulation Policies, Service Policies, investment and the general attitude of the government have significant effects on outward foreign direct investment in China at the national level (Tong Yin, Lisa De Propris, Liza Jabbour, 2021).

Foreign investment's choice in local level is changed by emission reduction target at city-level vary and environmental regulation helps improve the structure of foreign direct investment and contributes to business environment and industrial upgrading in the economy (Yuan Xu, Yanrui Wu, Yongli Shi, 2021). Dynamic institutional changes that impact at the actor level, which are largely neglected in research on the role of institutional change in foreign direct investment. German firms have long-term investment relationships in Turkey, such these relationships are impacted by both formal and informal institutions to respond to risks arising from shocks at a formal institutional level (Philip Völlers, Nuri Yavan, Martin Franz, 2021). According to Andrzej Cieślak, Mahdi Ghodsi (2021) that "The empirical evidence suggests that better economic sentiments in an European Union Member State attract multinational enterprises to undertake foreign direct investment in that country, while worse economic sentiments in European Union Member State motivate multinational enterprises in that country to invest abroad". foreign investments and firm value are negatively associated. Foreign investments are negatively related to firm performance at short and long terms. Foreign investments reduce revenue growth but do not have effect in firm efficiency. It is understood that simply increasing foreign investments does not mean necessarily enhance revenue growth or firm efficiency (Napaporn Likitwongkajon, Chaiporn Vithessonthi, 2020). The importance of foreign investment and concentration of firms with foreign investments to increase business competitiveness. It is also important investment zones to attract concentration of global firms and necessity for coordination and synchronization between municipalities and with international stakeholders at the megacity level (Adiwan F. Aritenang, 2021). Foreign Direct Investment is important part in the economic growth of developing Asia and logistics capability, foreign direct Investment is impacted by location choice (Keng Lin Soh, Wai Peng Wong, Chor Foon Tang, 2021). Betsy M. Oloyede, Evans S. Osabuohien, Jeremiah O. Ejemeyovwi, (2021) said that "There is a positive but insignificant nexus between economic growth rate and trade openness in both the combined simulated Economic Community of West African States and Southern African Development Community and the

individual regional economic communities. The government and other relevant stakeholders should ensure policies are enacted and enforced to transmit the experienced economic growth into substantial trade gains and further trade openness in Economic Community of West African States and Southern African Development Community". CO2 emissions, population density and trade openness negatively affect the economic growth in South Asia. There is a bidirectional causality between economic growth and CO2 emissions, and between trade openness and CO2 emissions. And there is a unidirectional causality running from trade openness to economic growth (Mohammad Mafizur Rahman, KaisSaidi, Mounir Ben Mbarek, 2020). Gideon Kwaku MinuaAmpofo, Jinhua Cheng, Daniel Akwasi Asante et al., (2020) indicate that "A positive shock to trade openness has a positive impact on economic growth in most of the countries. It is recommended the implementation of more trade liberalization policies to maximize the benefits from trade openness, especially in the countries where the "natural resource curse phenomenon reported".

III. Methodology

3.1. Study Framework.

3.2. Variables of study framework.

Independent variables:

IN₁ is investment from the government budget in HCM, unit is billion Vietnam Dong.

IN₂ is foreign investment in HCM, unit is thousand US Dollar.

OE is openness of economy in HCM.

Dependent variables:

Labour goods productivity (X₁):

$$X_1 = \frac{\text{Total volume of goods have been transported}}{\text{Total number of human resource}}$$

Labour passenger productivity (X₂):

$$X_2 = \frac{\text{Total number of passenger have been transported}}{\text{Total number of human resource}}$$

Capital goods productivity (X₃):

$$X_3 = \frac{\text{Total volume of goods have been transported}}{\text{Total capital}}$$

Capital passenger productivity (X₄):

$$X_4 = \frac{\text{Total number of passenger have been transported}}{\text{Total capital}}$$

Gross domestic products (X₅):

As by definition of HCM statistics department that "GDP of HCM transport logistics is the total transport logistics product in HCM, which are carried out by production and business units residing in HCM. X₅ is calculated by equal to the total value added at the base prices of all economic activities plus product taxes minus product subsidies".

3.3. Multivariate regression model.

$$X_1 = i_0 + i_1IN_1 + i_2IN_2 + i_3OE + j \quad (1)$$

$$X_2 = i_0 + i_1IN_1 + i_2IN_2 + i_3OE + j \quad (2)$$

$$X_3 = i_0 + i_1IN_1 + i_2IN_2 + i_3OE + j \quad (3)$$

$$X_4 = i_0 + i_1IN_1 + i_2IN_2 + i_3OE + j \quad (4)$$

$$X_5 = i_0 + i_1IN_1 + i_2IN_2 + i_3OE + j \quad (5)$$

Where

i₀ is the intersection of vertical axis and lines of regression.

j is other factors which are not IN₁, IN₂, OE that this paper does not have analysis.

Based on Keshab Bhattacharai (2015, p. 55) and Jeffrey M. Wooldridge (2020, p. 126) that is below:

i₀ + i₁ + i₂ + i₃ = 0 is to mean that (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5) are not built suitably to the input data and it does not have statistics significance.

i₀ + i₁ + i₂ + i₃ ≠ 0 is to mean (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5) are built suitably to the input data and it has statistics significance.

i₀ + i₁ + i₂ + i₃ > 0 means IN₁, IN₂, OE impact on X₁, X₂, X₃, X₄, X₅, respectively and separately.

i₀ + i₁ + i₂ + i₃ < 0 means IN₁, IN₂, OE do not impact on X₁, X₂, X₃, X₄, X₅, respectively and separately.

IV. Theoretical basis

4.1. Government investment.

Base on World Bank's definition that Government investment is "General government final consumption expenditure (formerly general government consumption) includes all government current expenditures for purchases of goods and services (including compensation of employees). It also includes most expenditures on national defence and security but excludes government military expenditures that are part of government capital formation."

4.2. Foreign investment.

According to World Bank, "Foreign direct investment refers to direct investment equity flows in the reporting economy. It is the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, and other capital. Direct investment is a category of cross-border investment associated with a resident in one economy having control or a significant degree of influence on the management of an enterprise that is resident in another economy. Ownership of 10 percent or more of the ordinary shares of voting stock is the criterion for determining the existence of a direct investment relationship. Data are in current U.S. dollars".

4.3. Openness of economy.

Based on definition of Vietnamese Government, openness of economy is calculated by two methods:

$$OE = \frac{\text{Total export turnover}}{GDP} \quad (\text{Method 1})$$

$$OE = \frac{\text{Total export turnover and service}}{GDP} \quad (\text{Method 2})$$

Author uses method 1 for this paper.

V. Data source

All data are from HCM Statistics Department and HCM Statistical Yearbook.

VI. Study results

Table 1: Results of MR models for relations between (1) IN₁+ IN₂+ OE and X₁, (2) IN₁+ IN₂+ OE and X₂, (3) IN₁+ IN₂+ OE and X₃

(1) IN ₁ + IN ₂ + OE and X ₁				(2) IN ₁ + IN ₂ + OE and X ₂				(3) IN ₁ + IN ₂ + OE and X ₃			
R square (RS)		0.86341502 (86%)		R square (RS)		0.5838768 (58%)		R square (RS)		0.42442333 (42%)	
Adjusted R Square (ARS)		0.8048786 (80%)		Adjusted R Square (ARS)		0.40553829 (41%)		Adjusted R Square (ARS)		0.17774761 (18%)	
Significance F (SF)		0.00207255		Significance F (SF)		0.08887196		Significance F (SF)		0.24930864	
Independent variables	Coefficients	Value of Coefficients (VC)	P-Value (PV)	Independent variables	Coefficients	Value of Coefficients (VC)	P-Value (PV)	Independent variables	Coefficients	Value of Coefficients (VC)	P-Value (PV)
	i ₀	1.03053683	0.00178384		i ₀	0.07842556	0.11843926		i ₀	0.8793584	0.0380915
IN ₁	i ₁	3.748E-06	0.40505915	IN ₁	i ₁	1.0861E-06	0.25889031	IN ₁	i ₁	-2.663E-06	0.71154606
IN ₂	i ₂	6.5123E-07	0.66766874	IN ₂	i ₂	3.3274E-07	0.30950351	IN ₂	i ₂	2.3215E-06	0.36104738
OE	i ₃	-14.485969	0.00180603	OE	i ₃	-0.7308247	0.27771337	OE	i ₃	-9.186351	0.10051693

Table 1 gives information of the results:

(1) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_1 :

$RS = 0.86341502$ (86%), $ARS = 0.8048786$ (80%) to tell the output of regression is explained 80% of input data. $i_0 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 = -13.45542798 \neq 0$, it defines that MR model was built to be suitable to the input data and has statistics significance is 0.00207255.

Value of Coefficients > 0 consists of $i_1 = 3.748E-06$ and $i_2 = 6.5123E-07$ which is evidence to confirm that IN_1 and IN_2 impact on X_1

Value of Coefficients < 0 is $i_3 = -14.485969$ that means OE does not impact on X_1

(2) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_2

$RS = 0.42442333$ (42%), $ARS = 0.40553829$ (41%) to tell the output of regression is explained 41% of input data. $i_0 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 = -0.652397693 \neq 0$, it defines that MR model was built to be suitable to the input data and has statistics significance is 0.08887196.

Value of Coefficients > 0 consists of $i_1 = 1.0861E-06$ and $i_2 = 3.3274E-07$ which is evidence to confirm that IN_1 and IN_2 impact on X_2

Value of Coefficients < 0 is $i_3 = -0.7308247$ that means OE does not impact on X_2

(3) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_3

$RS = 0.86341502$ (86%), $ARS = 0.17774761$ (18%) to tell the output of regression is explained 18% of input data. $i_0 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 = -8.306992931 \neq 0$, it defines that MR model was built to be suitable to the input data and has statistics significance is 0.24930864.

Value of Coefficients > 0 consists of $i_2 = 2.3215E-06$ which is evidence to confirm that IN_2 impacts on X_3

Value of Coefficients < 0 is $i_1 = -2.663E-06$ and $i_3 = -9.186351$ that means IN_1 and OE do not impact on X_3

Table 2: Results of MR models for relations between (4) IN₁+ IN₂+ OE and X₄, (5) IN₁+ IN₂+ OE and X₅

(4) IN ₁ + IN ₂ + OE and X ₄				(5) IN ₁ + IN ₂ + OE and X ₅			
R square (RS)		0.54139804 (54%)		R square (RS)		0.92410747 (92%)	
Adjusted R Square (ARS)		0.34485435 (34%)		Adjusted R Square (ARS)		0.8915821 (89%)	
Significance F (SF)		0.12173916		Significance F (SF)		0.00027195	
Independent variables	Coefficients	Value of Coefficients (VC)	P-Value (PV)	Independent variables	Coefficients	Value of Coefficients (VC)	P-Value (PV)
	i ₀	0.06489551	0.08003114		i ₀	67965.2093	0.09562426
IN ₁	i ₁	-6.749E-08	0.91847755	IN ₁	i ₁	2.65991428	0.00710354
IN ₂	i ₂	5.8534E-07	0.03162315	IN ₂	i ₂	0.38687904	0.15576912
OE	i ₃	-0.0297656	0.94875867	OE	i ₃	-2085574.5	0.00407097

(4) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_4

$RS = 0.54139804$ (54%), $ARS = 0.34485435$ (34%) to tell the output of regression is explained 34% of input data. $i_0 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 = 0.035130392 \neq 0$, it defines that MR model was built to be suitable to the input data and has statistics significance is 0.00027195.

Value of Coefficients > 0 consists of $i_2 = 5.8534E-07$ which is evidence to confirm that IN_2 impacts on X_4

Value of Coefficients < 0 is $i_1 = -6.749E-08$ and $i_3 = -0.0297656$ that means IN_1 and OE do not impact on X_4

(5) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_5

$RS = 0.92410747$ (92%), $ARS = 0.8915821$ (89%) to tell the output of regression is explained 89% of input data. $i_0 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 = -2017606.289 \neq 0$, it defines that MR model was built to be suitable to the input data and has statistics significance is 0.24930864.

Value of Coefficients > 0 consists of $i_1 = 2.65991428$ and $i_2 = 0.38687904$ which is evidence to confirm that IN_1 and IN_2 impact on X_5 .

Value of Coefficients < 0 is $i_3 = -2085574.5$ that means OE does not impact on X_5

VII. Discussion

From MR results are described in section 6, (1) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X is explained 80% of input data, IN_1 and IN_2 impact on X_1 , OE does not impact on X_1 . (2) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_2 is explained 41% of input data, IN_1 and IN_2 impact on X_2 , OE does not impact on X_2 . (3) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_3 is explained 18% of input data, IN_2 impacts on X_3 , IN_1 and OE do not impact on X_3 . (4) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_4 is explained 34% of input data, IN_2 impacts on X_4 , IN_1 and OE do not impact on X_4 . (5) $IN_1 + IN_2 + OE$ and X_5 is explained 89% of input data, IN_1 and IN_2 impact on X_5 , OE does not impact on X_5

VIII. Conclusion

Based on section 6 of study results and section 7 for discussion, the conclusion is (IN_1) investment from the government budget and (IN_2) foreign investment impact on (X_1) Labour goods productivity, (OE) openness of economy in HCM does not impact on (X_1) Labour goods productivity. (IN_1) investment from the government budget and (IN_2) foreign investment impact on (X_2) Labour passenger productivity, (OE) openness of economy does not impact on (X_2) Labour passenger productivity. (IN_2) foreign investment impacts on (X_3) Capital goods productivity, (IN_1) investment from the government budget and (OE) openness of economy do not impact on (X_3) Capital goods productivity. (IN_2) foreign investment impacts on (X_4) Capital passenger productivity, (IN_1) investment from the government budget and (OE) openness of economy do not impact on (X_4) Capital passenger productivity. (IN_1) investment from the government budget and (IN_2) foreign investment impact on (X_5) Gross domestic products, (OE) openness of economy does not impact on (X_5) Gross domestic products.

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